

Using Brain-Computer Interface in Cognitive Buildings: a Real-time Case Study.

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Abstract—Cognitive Buildings (CBs) are IoT-based smart infrastructures that self-learn, self-organize, and adapt through Artificial Intelligence (AI), thereby enhancing occupant satisfaction with minimal human intervention. Recent advances in wearable technology have enabled the integration of electroencephalogram (EEG) sensors into CBs, allowing continuous, unobtrusive monitoring of residents' states. In this paper, we propose a novel Cloud-Edge Brain-Computer Interface (BCI) system that leverages Steady-State Visually Evoked Potentials (SSVEPs) to provide real-time feedback to CBs. Our approach is validated through a comprehensive case study conducted at the IoT Laboratory of the ICAR-CNR headquarters in Rende (Italy), where a consumer-grade wearable EEG headset is integrated with embedded, edge, and cloud devices. Furthermore, we evaluate the performance of four machine learning algorithms deployed on an embedded Raspberry Pi 4 for SSVEP recognition, demonstrating the system's potential for real-time applications in CB environments.

Index Terms—Brain-Computer Interface (BCI), Edge-Cloud Continuum, Steady-State Visually Evoked Potentials (SSVEP), Wearables, Machine Learning, Cognitive Buildings, Embedded Intelligence.

I. INTRODUCTION

Cognitive Buildings (CBs) [1], [2] are Internet of Things (IoT)-based smart buildings endowed with capabilities that allow them to self-learn, self-organize, and self-adapt. CBs rely on Artificial Intelligence (AI) to collect and process building data, enabling them to adjust with minimal human intervention [3]. In recent years, the integration of wearables with CBs has significantly enhanced occupant satisfaction [4], [5]. This improvement is mainly due to CBs being able to receive continuous feedback from building inhabitants without requiring any specific actions on their part.

In this context, electroencephalogram (EEG) sensors worn by residents can provide CBs with valuable insights into their needs. For instance, if one of its occupants is stressed

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or feeling cold, a CB can be notified and adapt to this. Numerous studies have focused on interpreting EEG signals to better understand human needs [6]. These signals are used to implement the so-called Brain-Computer Interface (BCI) and can be classified into Event-Related and Spontaneous [4]. Among the Event-Related signals, Steady-State Visually Evoked Potentials (SSVEPs) are elicited by visual stimuli and can be detected by monitoring the occipital region with EEG sensors.

In this paper, we want to demonstrate how BCI technology can be applied in CBs for real-time applications. Specifically, we present the following contributions:

- The design of a Cloud-Edge BCI system for CBs.
- A real-time case study using embedded, edge, and cloud devices, implemented at the IoT Laboratory in the ICAR-CNR headquarters in Rende (Italy).
- The integration of a consumer-grade wearable EEG headset with the system to issue commands to CBs, focusing on the use of two EEG sensors in the occipital region for SSVEP stimulus recognition.
- A comparison of four machine learning algorithms deployed on an embedded Raspberry Pi 4 device for recognizing SSVEP stimuli.

Compared to state-of-the-art methods, our work is the first to implement a BCI system that collects EEG sensor data and makes SSVEP stimuli recognition on embedded devices, offering a novel and efficient solution for real-time CB applications.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II will overview the related work, Section III will introduce our system's design, and Section IV will show the implemented case study. Finally, Section V will conclude the paper.

II. STATE OF THE ART

The concept of machines interfacing directly with the human mind has captivated both science-fiction narratives and academic research for decades. In contemporary times, this vision is transitioning into a concrete reality due to the development of BCI systems.

While disability is a major application area for BCI, given the large number of affected patients, those interfaces can also be valuable in other scenarios, accurately capturing user feelings with minimal human interaction. Consequently, diverse applications have been developed to cater to a broad user base, particularly in smart home technology.

For example, the authors of [7] propose a hybrid EEG-based BCI system combined with head motion sensing for smart home control. The proposed BCI method allows the user to

control four different electronic appliances by extracting and processing the brain signal and head movements. The primary goal of the framework proposed in [8] is to achieve cost-effective results in a smart home environment: at this end, an IoT Smart Home Kit has been constructed to evaluate the framework on a scaled prototype. A digital twin, equipped with various sensors such as temperature, motion, and gas sensors, will act as an intermediary, translating brain signals into control commands for the physical assets. To improve device security, the paper in [9] introduced an EEG-based authentication method that allows users to lock and unlock personal devices after a two-stage verification based on mind-generated passwords.

The authors of [10] proposed the use of SSVEP technology to develop a smart home system enabling users to manipulate six different devices by responding to visual stimuli presented on multiple screens. Systems proposed by the community often demonstrate effective integration between BCI and AI components. The proposed system in [11] aims to improve SSVEP signal classification using machine learning algorithms. This involves extracting dominant frequency features and applying classifiers like Decision Tree, Linear Discriminant Analysis, and Support Vector Machine to achieve high accuracy with fewer EEG channels. Reducing channel count is crucial, as irrelevant EEG channels can introduce noise and redundant information, negatively impacting signal processing accuracy. In [12], deep machine learning models, including a one-dimensional convolutional neural network (1D CNN), were used to process signals from SSVEP devices, achieving high accuracy in classifying signals across five different frequencies.

To our knowledge, we observe that AI integration with BCIs is primarily utilized to enhance signal processing within the cloud, while its potential as a core functional component at the edge remains largely unexplored.

III. CLOUD-EDGE DESIGN OF A BCI SYSTEM

In this section, we introduce the design of a general BCI system based on SSVEP. Our design assumes that the system can be deployed along the edge-cloud continuum [13]. Accordingly, we specify where each component should be executed across the IoT, Edge, and Cloud layers. As illustrated in Figure 1, the architecture is organized as follows: (i) *IoT Layer*: this layer encompasses devices such as sensors, actuators, and smart objects; (ii) *Edge Layer*: this layer hosts devices that can be deployed within CBs. It contains system components (hereafter called *blocks*) that may run on one or more devices; (iii) *Cloud Layer*: this layer is reserved for components that require high-performance computing resources.

Figure 1 outlines the three architectural layers and illustrates the data flow between the different components to let the reader understand how EEG signals are acquired, processed, and utilized throughout the system. The system components are detailed below, following the flow of data:

- *EEG Sensors*: This block represents the EEG sensors that capture brain signals. The resulting *EEG Data* is

Fig. 1: The Proposed Cloud-Edge BCI System

transmitted to both the *Acquisition and Labeling* and *Model Execution* blocks.

- *Acquisition and Labeling*: In this block, EEG signals are acquired and annotated with corresponding labels, generating the dataset required for training the system. The *Labeled EEG Data* is then sent to the *SSVEP Model Training* block.
- *SSVEP Model Training*: Deployed in the cloud, this block trains a machine learning model using the labeled data. Once trained, the model is transferred to the *Model Execution* block located at the edge.
- *Model Execution*: This block runs the transferred model to classify incoming *EEG Data*. The output, referred to as *Recognized Activity*, is forwarded to the *Cognitive App* block.
- *Cognitive App*: This block receives the *Recognized Activity* and performs the appropriate actions (e.g., generating a message for the CB).

It is worth noting that the placement of the blocks is driven by performance requirements. For example, the SSVEP Model Training block is deployed in the Cloud layer to leverage its high computational power for model training, while the Model Execution block is situated at the Edge to minimize latency and provide real-time responses. Moreover, the design is inherently scalable and robust, allowing for the integration of additional devices at the IoT and Edge layers as system demands grow.

The implementation of a system based on this design is presented in the following section.

IV. CASE STUDY

This section will show the details of the case study implemented together with some preliminary results.

A. Real Implementation

The case study realized at the IoT Laboratory of the ICAR-CNR headquarters in Rende (Italy) is about the implementation

of an EEG-based BCI system that gives the user the ability to interact in real-time with a CB by observing a screen where SSVEP stimuli are provided in the form of flickering white squares (shown in Figure 2). A more detailed description of the implementation of the system's blocks, already introduced above, is presented below.

1) *EEG Sensors*: EEG signals are collected using the DIADEM¹ headset developed by BITBRAIN, a lightweight and wearable dry-EEG device designed for non-invasive brain activity monitoring. The headset is equipped with 12 channels, strategically placed across various locations on the scalp, including Fp1, Fp2, AF7, AF8, F3, F4, P3, P4, PO7, PO8, O1, and O2 [4]. This arrangement allows for comprehensive monitoring of brain activity across frontal, parietal, and occipital regions. The device operates with a high-precision sampling rate of 256 Hz, ensuring that the captured signals provide detailed temporal resolution for further analysis. In our case study, to reduce at a minimum the computation needed at the edge (specially in the Model Execution), we focus on using only the two electrodes O1 and O2, positioned in the occipital region, where SSVEP signals are predominantly detected.

2) *Acquisition and Labeling*: receives data from the EEG headset, adding to it specific labels associated with different phases of the experiment conducted, before sending it to the cloud for ML model training. In particular, the experiment consists of observing white squares flickering at 8.57 Hz, 10 Hz, and 12 Hz on a black LCD screen. The squares are placed at the bottom right, top, and bottom left corners, respectively, with a static central square included as a reference. The participant in the experiment is instructed to focus on one square per time (indicated by an arrow) for 7 seconds, following a randomized sequence with 16 repetitions per square. The experiment is carried out on a computer running software that facilitates both visual stimulus presentation and concurrent EEG data acquisition and labeling: Bitbrain Device Viewer - for real-time EEG visualization and signal export using the Lab Streaming Layer (LSL) protocol - and OpenVibe Suite² - for presenting visual stimuli through a graphical interface and acquiring EEG signals through the LSL protocol with annotated temporal markers.

3) *SSVEP Model Training*: processes the labeled EEG data received and trains the Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA), the Support Vector Machine (SVM), the Decision Tree (DT), and the Random Forest (RF) ML models for the recognition of SSVEP signals. The first step is the extraction and elaboration of EEG data time intervals of interest: the 7-second intervals with squares flickering are selected and reorganized in 2-second overlapping windows (shifted by 0.5 seconds). So, each 7-second interval is composed of 11 2-second windows. On each of these 2-second windows, bandpass and notch filters are applied, followed by PSD (Power Spectral Density) values

¹Bitbrain Diadem. <https://www.bitbrain.com/neurotechnology-products/dry-eeg/diadem>

²OpenVibe - Software for Brain-Computer Interface and Real Time Neurosciences. <https://openvibe.inria.fr/>

Fig. 2: Cognitive App GUI

calculation. These features are used to train and validate ML models. All these steps are implemented through Python scripts in the cloud.

4) *Model Execution*: receives the ML models trained in the cloud and applies them in real-time to the EEG data acquired from the headset, then sends the SSVEP signal recognition to the Cognitive App. This block has been developed on an embedded edge device (Raspberry Pi 4³), which has been interfaced with the EEG headset through Bluetooth communication. So, in real-time, it acquires EEG data, preprocesses it through filtering and PSD calculation, then applies the ML models and sends the recognized activities to the Cognitive App. The deployment of this block on the Raspberry Pi 4 is driven by the need for a portable solution that users can easily carry with them inside a CB. The integration of the DIADEM headset with the Raspberry Pi 4 faced challenges due to the lack of official ARM-compatible drivers. To overcome this, a virtualization-based solution was implemented using KVM [14], [15] and QEMU [16], [17], enabling the execution of a Debian 12 AMD64 environment on the Raspberry Pi 4 (ARMv8). KVM transformed the Linux kernel into a hypervisor that supports virtual machines, QEMU's dynamic binary translation allowed real-time execution of x86_64 code, albeit with some performance overhead. Additionally, USB passthrough was used to enable direct Bluetooth communication between the headset and the virtual machine, minimizing the EEG data transmission latency.

5) *Cognitive App*: is a Python App that displays on a screen 3 flickering white squares at the frequencies of 8.57 Hz, 10 Hz and 12 Hz, each associated with a status or command by the user, as shown in Figure 2. Furthermore, it receives the Recognized Activity message from the Model Execution component and acts accordingly on the CB. In our case study, this block has been deployed on a Raspberry Pi 4.

B. Preliminary Results

In this real-time case study, four classification algorithms have been tested, and the results are shown in Figures 3 and 4. As introduced above, for the SSVEP classification, 2-second intervals of EEG data collected from the O1 and O2 electrodes have been used. The results indicate that SVM achieves the highest overall accuracy (98.01%), followed closely by RF

³Raspberry Pi 4 website. <https://www.raspberrypi.com/products/raspberry-pi-4-model-b/>

Fig. 3: Classification Accuracy for different Algorithms

Fig. 4: Classification Accuracy for each stimulus for different Algorithms

(97.72%) and LDA (96.02%), while DT performs the worst (90.76%). SVM excels particularly at detecting 10 Hz (100%) stimuli, whereas RF performs best for 8.57 Hz (98.30%) and 12 Hz (97.73%), and LDA effectively distinguishes the No Flickering class (99.43%). DT shows lower accuracy across all classes, making it less suitable for our SSVEP classification. In general, our experiments demonstrate that SVM and RF are the most reliable classifiers for the proposed SSVEP recognition.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, we introduced a Cloud-Edge BCI system that leverages wearable EEG sensors and SSVEP signals to provide real-time commands to Cognitive Buildings. A real-time case study conducted at the IoT Laboratory of the ICAR-CNR headquarters validated the performance of our system using a consumer-grade wearable EEG headset and embedded, edge, and cloud devices. The experimental results demonstrated that, among the evaluated machine learning algorithms, SVM and RF achieved the highest overall accuracies — 98.01% and 97.72%, respectively — making them the most reliable classifiers for SSVEP recognition in our system. These findings underscore the potential of incorporating BCI technology into CB environments to enhance occupant satisfaction through adaptive and intelligent building management with minimal human intervention.

Future work will focus on expanding our dataset to include a larger number of subjects to improve model generalization, implementing and testing all the system components on

embedded devices to boost portability and robustness, and developing a unified communication interface to seamlessly integrate with broader cognitive environments, including robots and drones [18].

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Amadeo, F. Cicirelli, A. Guerrieri, G. Ruggeri, G. Spezzano, and A. Vinci, "When edge intelligence meets cognitive buildings: The cogito platform," *Internet of Things*, vol. 24, p. 100908, 2023.
- [2] F. Cicirelli, A. Guerrieri, G. Spezzano, and A. Vinci, "A cognitive enabled, edge-computing architecture for future generation iot environments," in *2019 IEEE 5th World Forum on Internet of Things (WF-IoT)*, 2019, pp. 35–40.
- [3] —, *IoT Edge Solutions for Cognitive Buildings*, ser. Internet of Things. Springer Cham, 2023.
- [4] L. Rizzo, P. Zicari, F. Cicirelli, A. Guerrieri, M. Micieli, and A. Vinci, "A study on consumer-grade eeg headsets in bci applications," in *IEEE Conf. on Pervasive and Intelligent Computing (PICom)*, 2024, pp. 67–74.
- [5] G. Aloï, F. Frustaci, R. Gravina, A. Guerrieri, G. Pio, and C. Savaglio, "Cocowears: A framework for continuum computing wearable systems," *Procedia Computer Science*, vol. 253, pp. 1525–1534, 2025, 6th International Conference on Industry 4.0 and Smart Manufacturing.
- [6] Y. Roy, H. Banville, I. Albuquerque, A. Gramfort, T. H. Falk, and J. Faubert, "Deep learning-based electroencephalography analysis: a systematic review," *Journal of neural engineering*, vol. 16, no. 5, p. 051001, 2019.
- [7] M. D. J. Arachchige, M. Nafea, and H. Nugroho, "A hybrid EEG and head motion system for smart home control for disabled people," *J. Ambient Intell. Humaniz. Comput.*, vol. 14, no. 4, pp. 4023–4038, 2023.
- [8] A. Zakzouk, K. Menzel, and M. Hamdy, "Brain-computer-interface (BCI) based smart home control using EEG mental commands," in *Collaborative Networks in Digitalization and Society 5.0 - 24th IFIP WG 5.5 Working Conference on Virtual Enterprises, PRO-VE 2023, Proceedings*, ser. IFIP Advances in Information and Communication Technology, vol. 688. Springer, 2023, pp. 720–732.
- [9] T. Hossain, A. rakshit, and A. Konar, "Brain-computer interface based user authentication system for personal device security," in *2020 International Conference on Computer, Electrical & Communication Engineering (ICCECE)*, 2020, pp. 1–6.
- [10] M. Adams, S. Ben-Salem, Z. Islam, A. Vogelsang, T. Jungeblut, U. Rückert, I. Volosyak, M. Benda, A. Saboor, A. F. Krause, A. Rezeika, F. Gembler, P. Stawicki, M. Hesse, and K. Essig, "Towards an SSVEP-BCI controlled smart home," in *2019 IEEE International Conference on Systems, Man and Cybernetics, SMC 2019*. IEEE, 2019, pp. 2737–2742.
- [11] V. Kanagaluru, "Artificial intelligence based bci using ssvep signals with single channel eeg," *Technology and Health Care*, p. 09287329241302740, 2025.
- [12] T. Nguyen and W. Chung, "A single-channel ssvep-based BCI speller using deep learning," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 1752–1763, 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2018.2886759>
- [13] D. Rosendo, A. Costan, P. Valduriez, and G. Antoniu, "Distributed intelligence on the edge-to-cloud continuum: A systematic literature review," *Journal of Parallel and Distributed Computing*, vol. 166, pp. 71–94, 2022.
- [14] A. F. Gentile, D. Macrì, E. Greco, and P. Fazio, "Overlay and virtual private networks security performances analysis with open source infrastructure deployment," *Future Internet*, vol. 16, no. 8, 2024.
- [15] —, "Iot ip overlay network security performance analysis with open source infrastructure deployment," *Journal of Cybersecurity and Privacy*, vol. 4, no. 3, pp. 629–649, 2024.
- [16] A. F. Gentile, D. Macrì, and F. Lamonaca, "Safeguarding sensitive data in the era of iot: A study on security protocols for distributed measurement systems," in *2024 IEEE International Workshop on Metrology for Living Environment (MetroLivEnv)*, 2024, pp. 390–396.
- [17] A. Francesco Gentile, E. Greco, and D. Luca Carnì, "A real network performance analysis testbed for encrypted mqtt in dms," in *2024 IEEE International Workshop on Metrology for Living Environment (MetroLivEnv)*, 2024, pp. 397–402.
- [18] F. D'Urso, C. Santoro, and F. F. Santoro, "Integrating heterogeneous tools for physical simulation of multi-unmanned aerial vehicles," in *CEUR Workshop Proceedings*, vol. 2215, 2018, p. 10 – 15.